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CONCEPT OF THE "NEW" MODEL OF PUBLIC GOVERNANCE

КОНЦЕПЦІЯ «НОВОЇ» МОДЕЛІ ПУБЛІЧНОГО УПРАВЛІННЯ

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Балан О.С., Добрянська Н.А., Смаровоз М.Г. Концепція «нової» моделі публічного управління. Оглядова стаття.

У статті розглянуто сучасну концепцію моделі публічного управління. Для вирішення поставлених завдань у статті використано наступні методи наукових досліджень: аналізу та синтезу, системного підходу, систематизації та узагальнення. Теоретичну та методологічну основу даного наукового дослідження складають праці вітчизняних та закордонних авторів. Пропонуються заходи щодо покращення публічного управління. Основними завданнями подальших досліджень у галузі «нової» концепції публічного управління є вдосконалення процесів систематизування роботи та створення механізму використання у подальшому. У статті представлено розвиток дисципліни «публічне управління» як складової частини політичної науки, виділено методологічні та політичні проблеми, що визначили його еволюцію, міждисциплінарні риси та нормативні основи вивчення.

Ключові слова: публічне управління, концепція «нової» моделі, еволюція моделі управління, менеджмент

Balan O.S., Dobrianska N.A., Smarovoz M.G. The concept of a "new" model of public administration. Review article.

The article considers the modern concept of the public administration model. To solve the tasks in the article the following research methods are used: analysis and synthesis, system approach, systematization and generalization. The theoretical and methodological basis of this research are the works of domestic and foreign authors. Measures to improve public governance are proposed. The main objectives of further research in the field of "new" concept of public administration is to improve the processes of systematization of work and create a mechanism for future use. The article presents the development of the discipline "public administration" as an integral part of political science, highlights the methodological and political issues that determined its evolution, interdisciplinary features and regulatory framework of study.

Keywords: public administration, concept of "new" model, evolution of management model, management

Public administration includes elements of description, explanation and understanding, practical use of knowledge of various scientific fields to improve political-administrative systems and normative reflection of values, norms and standards applied to state regulation and public policy. The essence of public administration is the ability of public authorities to convert the interests of groups of society into political decisions and successfully implement them. At the same time, the concepts of articulation and realization of society's demands by public authorities have significant differences in content due to historical epoch, type of society and economy, cultural values and traditions, expectations of the population, which determines differences in approaches and interpretations of public administration.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The tested developments of Schleiferas T., Fry A. have a certain interest for revealing the conceptual demand for a new model of public administration [3]. Barabashiv A.G., Utkina V.V. [13], Otaman-chuk G.V. [1] also studied this issue.

The study of the nature, content and features of public administration requires not only a retrospective look at the features of the formation and development of models of public administration and analysis of their current state. Analysis of existing trends and prognostic analysis of scenarios for the near future in the development of public administration models are also needed.

The aim of the article is to study the concept of public administration based on the analysis of foreign and domestic scientific sources, as well as to

determine the main factors that influenced its emergence in different countries.

The main part

Public administration is a scientific field that has its own related but relatively autonomous research areas:

- public management, i.e., operational and administrative aspects of the functioning of state bodies, including the civil service;
- analysis of state programs and policies (public policy), including strategic planning, regulatory impact assessment;
- interaction of the state and citizens (public affairs), including lobbying and business relations with state and municipal bodies (government relations, GR) [13].

In this sense, public administration can be defined as a system of cooperation of state, municipal, non-profit and mixed structures, designed to ensure the satisfaction of public interests and the solution of collective problems. Public administration, combining the activities of state, municipal, non-governmental (non-profit) organizations, in fact represents a public-state system of realization of national and local interests and production of public goods. Of course, public administration must take into account the autonomy of the individual, leaving him the opportunity to make independent choices. Therefore, the level of feedback, the public level of implementation of management decisions, where the interest is:

- interest groups (various public foundations, trade unions, ethnic, youth and other organizations with certain interests, parliamentary lobbies, etc.);
- relations directly with citizens (taxation, law-making and law enforcement practice, preparation and implementation of social programs);
- relations with commercial enterprises (their legal regulation, public-private partnership, etc.).

Analysis of the relationship between state and municipal authorities with the above subjects of public relations brings us directly to the political component of their activities.

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The first concepts of public administration emerged in the states of the Ancient East and Antiquity. Thus, the ancient authors were busy searching for an "ideal state" capable of guaranteeing general happiness. The author of the concept of moral management, which is carried out by philosophers, was Aristotle. He saw the state as a provider of the public good, operating on the principles of justice,

equalizing and distributing, which would reduce inequality and minimize conflict. In ancient Rome, the state was understood as the legal management of families. In the concept of the rule of law, the secular rulers of Rome saw a convenient weapon against corporate associations in their own society, with which they were in conflict, especially with feudal corporations and the church [10]. Concepts of the rule of law as a model of governance at different historical stages and with different depth and content were reproduced in all historical European and modern states and are now supported by the UN.

The victory of royal absolutism in the XVI century. led to the formation of absolute monarchies, which required an extensive apparatus of government. Beginning with Vincent de Gournet (1745), the bureaucratic concept of governing the state became widespread, and has become firmly entrenched in modern practice. To denote executive power, Vincent de Gourme in 1745 introduced the term "bureaucracy" into science. The bureaucratic concept of management was scientifically substantiated in the works of G. Hegel, D.S. Mill, A.A de Tocqueville, G. Mosque, and especially M. Weber.

In the second half of the XIX century. O. Conte developed an idealistic concept of government in the form of sociocracy. It was run by the capitalist class (patricians), led by bankers. Philosophers, scientists, poets and physicians exercised spiritual power, and the government had to constantly awaken the idea of the whole and a sense of general solidarity [10, 16].

The industrial revolution that began in Western Europe led to increased centralization and bureaucratization of state power. In addition, the consequence of industrialization was the displacement of aristocratic elites by the nascent bourgeoisie. There was a period of critical reassessment of the experience of representative government and liberal-democratic values. This was reflected in the creation of the concept of elites by W. Pareto and in the concept of the political class of R. Mosca, who considered the elites the most valuable element of society, which have the right to govern.

In the early twentieth century. T. Veblen (USA) initiated the formation of a technocratic concept of government as a protest against the domination of the emerging financial oligarchy, which limited the interests of technology and production. The main idea was to transfer power to management specialists, technicians and engineers. This is how the slogan of radical anti-democratic technocracy of the 1930s was formed. XX century (G. Scott, S. Chase – USA, J. Bend – France).

The technocratic concept became widespread in the 1950's and 1960's, and included Weber's transformed "theory of bureaucracy" (Germany). According to J. Galbraith (USA), the state should have been transformed into an executive body of "technostructure". But then part of the theory of "post-industrial society" was the idea of the ruling "meritocracy" (the power of "deserving persons"), which obscured the fact of subordination of labor to capital.

In the 1990s. the concept of post-bureaucratic government began to take shape. Within the framework of this concept in 1992, D. Osborne and T. Gatlber formed the rules of effective administration:

- to direct development so as not to float downstream;
- empower citizens;
- maintain competition;
- the activity was determined by orders, not installations;
- focus on the result, not on the process or the funds used;
- the interests of customers outweighed the interests of the bureaucracy;
- entrepreneurial thinking: benefits, not costs;
- preventive forecasting and prevention of difficulties, not patching holes in a sinking ship, and therefore conceptual cooperation with the public [5].

The concept of post-bureaucratic governance initiated the formation of a new paradigm, commonly known as the "new public administration" (NPM). Outsourcing (i.e. outsourcing), i.e. the transfer of public functions to private organizations has become the main idea, the negative side of which is the reduction of the professional level of the official. According to the assessment of public services outsourcing by L. Zidentop [6], the "client" model had a negative impact only on the level of responsibility of citizens. It is obvious that the assessment of the effectiveness of the state within the concept of post-bureaucratic governance should be given by society. The representative of institutionalism D. North, exploring the functions of government, identified two concepts: exploitative and contractual.

The exploitative concept was built on the protection of property rights, maximizing the rent of the ruler, even to the detriment of society [7]. The contract concept provided that the economic order should be organized by the state.

According to O.M. Oliynyk, the essence of the contract state was the achievement of such a distribution of property rights that maximizes the total income of society through the transfer of transactions into the hands of those economic entities that can dispose of them optimally [8, 17].

Meanwhile, the practice of applying the idealistic provisions of the contractual concept of government has revealed a number of its shortcomings. Thus, in the second decade of the 2000s, the concept of the contract state became the main target of critics because of its support by large corporations and the financial sector to the detriment of the interests of the population. The avalanche-like increase in the number and value of public-private contracts has become, according to critics, a "golden field for corruption," and the marketing of public services has been seen as a threat to democracy and constitutionalism.

Analysis of the impact of globalization and decentralization allowed D. Cattle to formulate the concept of "government", in which the management process is carried out by the government and

institutions of social action, which could be both governmental and non-governmental [10]. However, P. Light believed that the current model of governance in the United States could not become part of the concept of "government" due to the lengthy procedures for hiring new employees due to excessive verification procedures, the predominance among newcomers of people focused not on business but on purely personal material interests, excessive growth of the number of hierarchical ladders in the ladder of positions, which increased from 17 (1960) to 33 (1992), then from 51 (1998) and to 64 (2004), and young people, which, according to its values and character, focused on public activities, lost interest in career and other opportunities offered by the civil service. [11]. It was expected that the weakening of the influx of young people will lead to the fact that in 2016.in the US civil service will be 60% of employees of retirement age, and among top federal officials – 90%.

The current post-industrial society is characterized by the diversity and mobility of the needs of the population, their growing individualization. Only short-lived models of public administration, which combine the high capacity of the state apparatus and clear strategic planning, can satisfy such fleeting demands. Conceptual understanding of the possibility of such a synthesis is presented in many new concepts of public administration.

An important place in this series of theories is occupied by the concepts of "new public management" (New Public Management from the 1980s to the 2000s), "e-government" (Digital Government), "network management" (Network model of Government), "anti-crisis state management" Anti-crisis Public Administration, "Good Governance", "Open Government Partnership". In addition, the development of the conceptual demand for a new model of public administration is the opinion of Schleifer A., Fry T. [2].

According to the following three models of government: "invisible hand", "hand aid" and "hand robbery" [2, 18]. The accumulated experience of application of the specified models of public administration shows that each of them has advantages and good results in the decision of only a specific range of problems, thus possessing an objective limit of the application. Therefore, the methodology of choosing one or another model for its incorporation into the mechanism of governing the current state is of practical importance.

According to O.V. Okhotsky, an effective model of public administration must meet the basic requirements:

- help evaluate results and make plans for the future;
- to create the possibility of using comparative strategic analysis taking into account the obtained effect;
- take into account the peculiarities of rhythm, direction and cyclical-wave nature of society [14, 19].

The need to apply New Public Management (NPM) – the model of "new public management" was caused by the growing demands of citizens to the quality of public services provided, as well as the effectiveness of management decisions by the executive authorities and public policy. In this regard, the problems of using private sector management technologies in the public sector and the relevant public law regulation have become relevant.

Criteria for the functioning of the NPM – model should be to maximize the quality and scope of government functions and services while minimizing budget funds. At the same time, the NPM model is required to build a system of trust between government, business and citizens according to the rules of freedom of public choice. The guiding principles of the NPM model are:

- development of the private sector;
- the state acts as a guarantor, public auditor, guarantor and customer of services;
- management of state organizations based on real results, not "mastered" budgets.

The main components of NPM – models in public administration:

- use of tools of program – target planning, budgeting, effective public-private partnership, constructive dialogue of citizens and the power;
- guidance on the criteria of legitimate lobbying, high quality of bureaucratic structures, gradual reduction of maintenance costs for civil servants, a high level of control;
- the use of management technologies that are successfully used in the private sector [14, 20].

Predicted advantages of NPM – model:

- the priority of goals and objectives over bureaucratic rules;

- creating conditions in the civil service for the implementation of initiative and independence;
- the use of modern technologies for personnel and information management, reducing the cost of maintaining the administration;
- reducing the cost of quality public services, transforming the apparatus into an effectively functioning public body;
- application of contractual relations and tender procedures in the public sector;
- transfer of redundant government functions to the private sector through outsourcing;
- building a system of remuneration based on meritocratic values.

Like any tool, the NPM model is not without its drawbacks and has limitations in its application, which have been noted in the literature. The concept of a new model of public administration

The traditional concept of management in the public sector was implemented in practice through the model of public administration (English – public administration), neoclassical concept of management – also in the form of public management (English - public management), the current concept of management – a form of new management (English New public management).

The word "public administration", which replaced the word "public administration", was first used by the British government Desmond Keeling in 1972. "Public administration is the best way to use resources to achieve priority goals. national policy".

The emergence of a new form of governance in the public sector was due to the need to improve the coordination structures and operations they use, so that all public institutions without exception work better. Public leadership belongs to the effective functioning of the whole concept of socio-political universities [15, 19].

Figure 1. Evolution of the governance model in the public sector

Source: authors' own development

The new administrative concepts rely on the comparison of the basics of management of individual and public sections, which for the purpose of a high-class leader is not much different than to regulate, because the texture of the social section can be analyzed by analogy with the texture of business.

According to this schedule, residents should be treated rationally as well as buyers of public institutions seeking to purchase specific administrative services. The main characteristics of services and a special type of good – invisibility,

inseparability from use, inability to save, a significant level of uncertainty – cause the characteristic conditions for their "production" and provision in public administration.

Property, timeliness, integrity, focus, competence and practicality for the sole purpose of the recipients become significant characteristics of the effectiveness of the social department. Motivation and analysis of the work of municipal employees are also performed in accordance with the analogy with the relevant market operations. The national leadership, according

to supporters of the market schedule, should be commercial.

Thus, there is a need to change the criteria for assessing the quality of government: from assessing the productivity of the course to the productivity of the result, the acquisition of which involves minimizing costs and allows to understand the problems of profitability of government agencies [1].

The effectiveness of government administration is largely related to awareness of policy and socio-political processes, but also the ability of government agencies to work with policy projects in a political context.

At present, the head of government must assume personal responsibility through the results of governance in the form of political accountability (according to the elected parliament and voters) and administrative responsibility (according to the government and other governing bodies).

At the heart of government marketing are the basic principles of the new concept of social responsibility, changing the relationship between government and residents, in which case there is a bureaucracy in the classical view and the environment in full. The intersection of political and administrative elements in public administration sets special conditions for civil servants [2, 19].

In some cases, they may function relatively independently of political interference, in others the political component is predominant, and in some cases the political and administrative elements are effectively combined.

The new form of public administration emphasizes the need to transform large government buildings into semi-independent institutions with a significant degree of physical activity, the ability to compete and the tendency to make dangerous decisions. But there are double views on the possibilities of competitiveness among government agencies, because along with the incentive there are also negative results from the differences between government and commercial institutions, the inability to use the simplest marketing devices to manufacture and promote them as well as variations of public amenities [12].

Insufficiency of competitive regulation, quality of services is a consequence of objective qualification of state bodies and financial inexpediency of duplication of their functions. For this reason, there is a need to separate trade functions from non-trade, political and

advisory functions – from the provision of services in the field of regulatory functions of state organizations.

In addition to coordination, the form of public administration is determined by a new type of public sector decision-making, which involves improving control and accountability based on clear and reliable information on the performance of all functions - social services, but also data on budget planning processes. The implementation of the basics of management in public administration is based on five types of personal control as well as the required minimum number in order to make the government accountable.

- legal supervision (legislative regulation);
- economic supervision (as well as municipal resources are spent);
- socio-political supervision (the result is fuller, the implementation of electoral obligations and hopes);
- democratic oversight (information is also consulting with selective bodies, relationships with population);
- moral supervision (influences in accordance with these moral norms) [14].

Conclusions

It is believed that the main features of public administration are its authoritarian nature, the origins of which are the will of the state and the spread of society. The interpretation of public administration as the authoritarian influence of the state on the social system is the best illustration of how the meaning of the term "public administration" is perceived and understood in Ukraine. The key aspect of public administration is the state, while the key aspect of public administration is the people. It should be noted that in Armenia and Moldova, a new term "public administration" has appeared.

In post-totalitarian countries, there are scientific discussions about the transition from public to public administration. Given that the management of any organization (enterprise, non-profit organization or government agency) in a market economy and democracy is different than in a centralized command-and-control system, public administration as an activity should also change. Thus, the classical model of governance in the public sector is gaining recognition in Ukraine, where the term "public administration" is still used, which is not an exact equivalent of the term "public administration" and is closer in meaning to the term "public administration".

Abstract

Public administration can be described as a system of cooperation of state, municipal, non-profit and mixed structures, designed to meet public interests and solve collective problems, combining them, in fact, represents a public-state system of national and local interests and production of public goods.

The first concepts of public administration emerged in the states of the Ancient East and Antiquity. Thus, the ancient authors were busy searching for the "ideal state" that could be the guarantor of common happiness.

The current post-industrial society is characterized by the diversity and mobility of the needs of the population, their growing individualization. Only short-lived models of public administration, which combine the high capacity of the state apparatus and clear strategic planning, can satisfy such fleeting demands.

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The emergence of a new form of governance in the public sector was due to the need to improve the coordination structures and operations they use, so that all public institutions without exception work better. Public leadership belongs to the effective functioning of the whole concept of socio-political universities.

Thus, the new form of public administration emphasizes the need to transform large government buildings into semi-independent institutions with a significant degree of physical activity, the ability to compete and the tendency to make dangerous decisions.

New administrative concepts rely on the comparison of the basics of management of individual and public sections, which for the purpose of a high-class leader is not much different than to regulate, because the texture of the social section can be analyzed by analogy with the texture of business. According to this schedule, it is rational to treat residents in the same way as buyers of public institutions seeking to purchase specific administrative services.

The need to use New Public Management – a model of "new public management" was caused by the growing demands of citizens to the quality of public services provided, as well as the effectiveness of management decisions by the executive and public policy. In this regard, the problems of using private sector management technologies in the public sector and the relevant public law regulation have become relevant.

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